

Supplementary material:

Table S1: Compounds in standard mixture

Standard solutions			
2,5-Dihydroxybenzoic acid	Asparagine	Glycine	Pimelic acid
2-Aminobutyric acid	Aspartic acid	Glycolic acid	Proline
2-Hydroxybutyric acid	Azelaic acid	Guanine	Putrescine
2-Hydroxyisocaproic acid	Benzoic acid	Guanosine	Pyroglutamic acid
2-Hydroxyphenylacetic acid	Betaine	Hippuric acid	Pyruvic acid
2-Ketoglutaric acid	Cellobiose	Histamine	Quinic acid
2-Methyl-hippuric acid	Choline	Histidine	Ribose
2-Hydroxyisovaleric acid	Cinnamic acid	Homogentistic acid	Salicylic acid
3-(3-hydroxyphenyl)-3-hydroxypropionic acid	Citramalic acid	Hypotaurine	Sarcosine
3,4-Dihydroxycinnamic acid	Citric acid	Indole-3-acetic acid	Sebacic acid
3,4-Dihydroxyphenylacetic acid	Citrulline	Inosine	Serine
3-Aminoisobutyric acid	Coumaric acid	Isoleucine	Sorbose
3-Hydroxy-3-methylglutaric acid	Creatine	Itaconic acid	Stigmasterol
3-Hydroxybutyric acid	Creatinine	Kynurenic acid	Suberic acid
3-Methyl adipic acid	Cysteine	Lactic acid	Succinic acid
3-Methylglutaric acid	Cystine	Lactose	Tartaric acid
3-Methylglutaric acid	Ethanolamine	Leucine	Taurine
3-Methylglutamic acid	Ethylmalonic acid	Malic acid	Thiamine
3-Phenyllactic acid	Fucose	Malonic acid	Threonine
4-Aminobutyric acid	Fumaric acid	Mandelic acid	Thymine
4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	Galactose	Mannitol	Tryptophan
4-Hydroxy-proline	Gallic acid	Mesaconic acid	Tyrosine
5-Hydroxy-3-indoleacetic acid	Gluconic acid	Methionine	Uracil
Acetoacetic	Glucuronic acid	Methylsuccinic acid	Valine

Aconitic acid	Glucose	Myo-Inositol	Vanillylmandelic acid
Alanine	Glutaconic acid	N-Acetylaspartic acid	Xanthurenic acid
Anthranillic acid	Glutamic acid	Ornithine	Xylitol
Arabinose	Glutaric acid	Oxalic acid	Xylose
Arginine	Glyceric acid	Oxaloacetic acid	γ -Aminobutyric acid
Ascorbic Acid	Glycerol	Phenylalanine	Methylmalonic acid

Table S2: Order of GC-MS analysis

Order of analysis									
1	Blank	31	C01_6	61	QC_9	91	C18_6	121	C30_3
2	Standard Mix	32	C07_6	62	C09_12	92	C22_3	122	C32_1
3	QC_FAME_1	33	C06_6	63	C11_1	93	QC_14	123	C29_1
4	QC_1	34	C01_12	64	C11_6	94	C23_3	124	QC_19
5	C06_3	35	C04_6	65	C11_3	95	C23_12	125	C28_1
6	C08_1	36	C07_3	66	C17_12	96	C22_12	126	C28_6
7	C01_1	37	QC_5	67	C10_1	97	C21_6	127	C27_12
8	C03_12	38	Standard Mix	68	QC_10	98	C18_12	128	C31_3
9	C07_1	39	QC_FAME_2	69	C17_6	99	C19B_3	129	C25_1
10	C05_3	40	QC_6	70	C10_12	100	QC_15	130	C30_6
11	C03_3	41	C14_1	71	C15_3	101	C23_6	131	C27_3
12	QC_2	42	C13_1	72	C15_12	102	C24_6	132	C31_6
13	C02_3	43	C15_1	73	C14_12	103	C21_1	133	QC_20
14	C04_1	44	C17_1	74	C16_3	104	C23_1	134	C30_12
15	C02_6	45	C15_6	75	C11_12	105	C19_3B	135	C32_12
16	C05_1	46	C09_3	76	QC_11	106	C20_1	136	C26_6
17	C06_1	47	QC_7	77	Standard Mix	107	C20_12	137	C26_3
18	C04_3	48	C10_3	78	QC_FAME_3	108	QC_16	138	C29_6
19	C02_1	49	C16_6	79	QC_12	109	C18_1	139	C25_6
20	QC_3	50	C17_3	80	C19B_6	110	C24_1	140	C27_6
21	C06_12	51	C09_6	81	C21_3	111	C19_12	141	C32_3
22	C04_12	52	C13_12	82	C18_3	112	QC_17	142	QC_21
23	C08_6	53	C13_3	83	C24_3	113	Standard Mix	143	C29_12
24	C01_3	54	QC_8	84	C22_1	114	QC_FAME_4	144	C32_6
25	C07_12	55	C10_6	85	C22_6	115	QC_18	145	C28_12
26	C02_12	56	C09_1	86	QC_13	116	C27_1	146	C29_3
27	C08_3	57	C14_3	87	C21_12	117	C26_1	147	C30_1
28	QC_4	58	C16_1	88	C19_1	118	C28_3	148	C26_12
29	C03_1	59	C13_6	89	C20_6	119	C25_3	149	C25_12
30	C03_6	60	C14_6	90	C19_6	120	C31_1	150	QC_22

Table S3. List of identified metabolites in Retention Index QC samples using MS-DIAL software.

Metabolites	RT	m/z	Derivatives
Alanine	7.3	116, 73	2 TMS
2-Hydroxyisovaleric acid	8.2	219, 145	2 TMS
Valine	8.8	144, 218	2 TMS
Benzoic acid	9.4	179, 105	1 TMS
Leucine	9.6	158, 102	2 TMS
Isoleucine	9.6	158, 218, 159	3 TMS
Proline	10.0	142	2 TMS
Glycine	10.1	174, 248	3 TMS
Glyceric acid	10.4	189, 103	3 TMS
Fumaric acid	10.7	245	2 TMS
Serine	10.8	204,218, 100	3 TMS
Threonine	11.4	117,218, 101	3 TMS
Malic acid	12.4	233,75	3 TMS
4-Hydroxyproline	12.9	230,140	3 TMS
Pyroglutamic acid	12.9	156, 84	2 TMS
Aspartic acid	12.9	232,100	3 TMS
Cysteine	13.3	220, 100	3 TMS
Glutamic acid	14.1	246, 128	3 TMS
Phenylalanine	14.2	218, 192,100	2 TMS
Asparagine	14.6	116,231	3 TMS
Citric acid	16.2	273,363	4 TMS
Ornithine	16.2	142,174	4 TMS
Galactose	17.0	319, 205	5 TMS
Glucose	17.3	205,117,175	5 TMS
Histidine	17.3	154,254,155	3 TMS
Tyrosine	17.5	179, 208	3 TMS
Gluconic acid	18.0	333, 292	6 TMS
Myo-inositol	18.9	217, 305, 191	6 TMS
Tryptophan	20.1	202, 73, 291	3 TMS
Cellobiose	24.2	204, 361, 217	8 TMS
Lactic acid	6.9	117	2 TMS
Glycolic acid	7.1	177	2 TMS
2-Hydroxybutyric acid	7.6	131,75,133	2 TMS
2-Aminobutyric acid	8.3	130,73	2 TMS
Succinic acid	10.2	75,247,55	2 TMS
Uracil	10.5	241	2 TMS
3-Aminoisobutyric acid	12.1	131	3 TMS
2-Ketoglutaric acid	13.6	198, 147	2 TMS

Xylose	14.5	103, 217,307	4 TMS
Ribose	14.7	103, 217	4 TMS
Sorbose	17.0	147, 307	5 TMS
Inosine	23.1	73, 230	4 TMS
Stigmasterol	28.1	83, 129	1 TMS

Table S4. %RSD values of peak areas for the 30 compounds in the samples stored after derivatisation and for the samples stored as dried extract. The %RSD was also calculated for the peaks normalized with the internal standard and injection standard.

Compounds	RSD%					
	Storage in freezer after derivatisation			Storage of dried extract		
	Raw	Internal Standard	Injection Correction	Raw	Internal Standard	Injection Correction
Alanine	20.5	17.0	19.9	26.7	16.5	22.0
2-Hydroisovaleric acid	11.8	12.5	16.7	14.6	12.2	18.5
Valine	16.7	14.9	24.3	29.3	22.3	29.3
Benzoic acid	21.1	19.1	20.7	29.0	18.3	22.0
Leucine	25.1	41.9	42.9	32.9	33.4	40.0
Isoleucine	30.3	29.4	38.2	29.9	27.9	37.4
Proline	51.8	57.6	59.2	49.7	51.8	53.9
Glycine	16.4	15.4	25.4	29.7	28.1	38.9
Glyceric acid	9.6	6.9	12.3	20.1	11.1	17.7
Fumaric acid	10.1	8.7	16.9	24.3	12.4	18.2
Serine	27.5	24.3	36.2	28.0	24.0	37.1
Threonine	15.9	12.2	26.6	16.2	15.6	26.9
Malic acid	10.1	6.3	12.9	28.1	13.5	19.1
Aspartic acid	23.0	20.0	31.4	25.5	30.9	34.9
Hydroxyproline	9.1	8.9	16.1	21.4	17.1	27.4
Pyroglutamic acid	11.6	9.7	12.2	31.6	22.1	26.3
Cysteine	22.1	23.2	28.1	30.6	30.5	33.2
Glutamic acid	14.4	13.8	20.4	21.7	21.4	28.2
Phenylalanine	18.2	17.2	25.4	22.4	25.7	31.0
Asparagine	12.2	7.3	15.9	27.7	12.9	21.1
Citric acid	11.3	10.1	13.7	24.4	15.6	21.0
Ornithine	16.9	14.6	22.1	29.3	16.2	25.4
Galactose	6.4	10.0	16.0	12.5	13.2	18.9
Glucose	10.2	7.6	14.7	21.1	12.8	20.1
Histidine	21.8	19.8	27.4	35.9	21.9	30.8
Tyrosine	11.1	8.7	15.9	25.8	12.9	20.1
Gluconic acid	13.0	8.9	13.5	24.0	11.0	17.2
Inositol	9.1	7.5	13.1	22.1	11.2	17.8
Tryptophan	12.6	8.7	12.6	27.6	13.7	19.8
Cellobiose	15.4	18.7	26.7	17.9	21.6	27.7

Figure S1: Sample preparation procedure

4) Figure S2: Strategy for the stability assessment during method development. Five groups of QC samples were prepared, with each group consisting of five replicates, a) The first group was analyzed immediately following derivatisation, b,c) The second and third groups were stored in the freezer for 24 hours and 48 hours, respectively, post-derivatisation, d,e) The fourth and fifth groups were stored as dried extracts in the freezer for 24 hours and 48 hours.

Figure S3: Box plots of the statistical significant metabolites contributing to differentiation of samples collected at various time points.

